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Navigating Organizational Inertia: “The Boundary Role of Self-Leadership in Shaping Employee Performance”

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Abstract

This study observes the effect of organizational inertia on employee performance and explores the moderating role of self-leadership in alleviating this relationship. Organizational inertia, described as resistance towards change and rigid practices rigid structures, entrenched routines, and resistance to change, is debated to decrease employee performance specifically in dynamic business environments. Quantitative research design is adopted in this research and data is collected from 400 respondents working in four major State-Owned Enterprises between October and December 2025 through structured questionnaires. Proposed relationships was tested through Structural equation modeling technique. The outcomes of the research show that there is a significant negative relationship between organizational inertia and employee performance outcomes, but self-leadership is a key moderator that weakening this negative relationship among inertia and performance. This is an important contribution towards organizational behavior literature by emphasizing self-leadership as an important boundary condition that eliminates the negative outcomes of inertia. Practically, the judgements of the study recommend that organizations who are working in inertia based conditions should emphasize in self-leadership improvement programs to heighten employee adaptability and sustain performance.

Keywords: Organizational Inertia, Self-Leadership, Employee Performance Structural Equation Modeling, State-Owned Enterprises, Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

In an era where businesses are facing extraordinary technological and geopolitical instability, organizations are not surviving better with stagnant structure and policies because it effects their ability to innovate for the sustainable performance (Alkharmany, Abdelhamid, & Elnokrashy, 2024). As an inertia concept, which interprets that how structural rigidities, and typical behaviors propagate resistance to change, this phenomenon not only decrease organizational dexterity for change, but also leads to performance failures (Ibrahim, Elzek, & Elsawalhy, 2024). Current studies highlight inertia's unescapable impact, such businesses where unrelated diversification worsens resource allocation inertia, hampering strategic regulations (Zhen, Cao, Qiu, & Xie, 2021).

State-owned enterprises (SOEs) are the key pillars of economic development especially in emerging markets driving revenues and employment. In Pakistani SOEs such as power and energy, transportation, communication, and financial sectors serve a central role in supporting national economic objectives and assisting initiatives like China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) (Hussain & Mohtar, 2017). Despite their strategic importance, these administrative units often face systemic challenges, comprising bureaucratic inflexibility and

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resistance for technological acceptance, which are aggravated by Pakistan's unstable economic and geopolitical environment (Sayed, Yasin, El, & Qoura, 2025). But according to the studies the primary reason of these challenges is organizational inertia, a phenomenon consists upon embedded routines, rigid structures, and cultural resistance to change, which ultimately reduce employee performance (Sayed et al., 2025).

In SOEs, specifically about Pakistani public sectors this inertia is augmented by factors such as political intervention, hierarchical strictness and resource constraints (Hussain & Mohtar, 2017). Recent studies show inertia's damaging effects on employee performance, and productivity (Asim, Akhtar, Amjad, & Latif, 2025). Correspondingly, a study discovered that inertia mediates the relationship between administrative culture and employee stillness, which ultimately reduce innovation and performance (Botke & van Woerkom, 2023). Global emerging economies, such as Indonesia, demonstrate that inertia hinders adaptability leads to performance deficits (B. Liu, Li, & Zhong, 2025). The influence of inertia on performance works at both individual and organizational levels. At individual level, it displays as reduced motivation, burnout and depress initiative (Qalati, Zafar, Fan, Sánchez Limón, & Khaskheli, 2022). Organizationally, inertia delays technological and regulatory responses that discourage competitiveness (Zhen et al., 2021).

While inertia raise significant challenges, but there are some moderators that mitigate its impact and increase performance outcomes of employees. Self-leadership appears as a capable moderator which defined as the process by which individuals set goals for own and motivate themselves (Hartadi & Sujoko, 2025). Self-leadership basically a strategy followed by individuals or groups, such as goal-setting and self-observation, which enable employees to cope organizational constraints and maintain performance instead of inertial environments (Jamaluddin, Razak, & Rahim, 2025). Recent literature supports this view, that self-leadership certainly moderates the relationship between inertia and employee work performance in public sector workplaces (Tetteh, 2024). A study reveals that self-leadership heightens work performance of employees by nurturing autonomy and ethics, minimizing the effects of bureaucratic rigidity (Chang & Yoo, 2025). The suggested study is grounded through different theoretical framework that integrates (SCT) Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 2001) and (SET) Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964) offers a strong basis for the study. These theories mutually deliver a pervasive understanding to appraise the multifaceted dynamics of organizational inertia and its effect on employee performance outcomes. Moreover, the moderation framework leverages these theories to describe how

Even with these insights, substantial gaps remain in the literature. Inertia's impact on performance has been studied in various frameworks (Sayed et al., 2025), and self-leadership's role in enabling employee empowerment is well-documented (Doiron, 2023), but no one is studied within the unique context of Pakistani SOEs. Especially in public sector settings where diverse challenges magnify inertia's effects, research on self-leadership as a moderator is scarce (Aslam, Ashraf, Iqbal, & Shabbir, 2024). Moreover, existing studies

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mostly focused upon private or Western organizations and overlooking the emerging markets like Pakistan (Arslan, Kanwal, Kazmi, & Rahman, 2023). This study reports this gap by inspecting the effect of organizational inertia on employee performance in Pakistani SOEs, where self-leadership serves as a moderator.

The main purpose of this research is to observe the impact of organizational inertia on employee performance outcomes where self-leadership playing as a critical moderator to mitigate this relationship. Finally, the study wants to examine the direct impact of self-leadership on employee performance, thus dealing empirical insights that how self-regulatory mechanism at individual level can effect performance in inertia based organizational conditions.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Organizational Inertia

Organizational inertia is an important phenomenon in the subject of organizational behavior which described as resistance against change, focused on established practices and bureaucratic strictness, which significantly affects the employee performance outcomes (Moradi, Jafari, Doorbash, & Mirzaei, 2021). Organizational inertia studied here through insight (cognitive difference for change), action (behavioral conflict for implementing change), and psychological perspectives (emotional resistance). Insight viewpoint of inertia means, where organizations mostly rely on outdated knowledge and old practices (Zhen et al., 2021). The action side highlights operational inflexibility, such as apposing to accepting new expertise or strategies (Feng, Li, & Xiong, 2024). While the psychological perspective of inertia means that employee behaviors and attitudes, such as fear of insecurity (X. Zhang, Shen, & Xu, 2024). Modern studies discuss this concept of inertia as it nurtures from operational, traditional, and structural reasons, which directly affect the organizational level adoptability (Zolak Poljašević, Gričnik, & Šarotar Žižek, 2025). In the same way, inertia also arises from embedded hierarchal mentalities and bureaucratic systems, which negatively affect novelty and responsiveness (Godkin, 2015).

2.2 Self-Leadership

Rapidly changing era through technological disruptions, and growing demands for individual autonomy, self-leadership has appeared as a key behavioral concept for improving personal and professional effectiveness (Linnenborn & Borchert, 2025). It defined as a process of self-influence through which individuals adjust their thoughts, and emotions to attain self-motivation (Botke & van Woerkom, 2023). This concept, rooted in social cognitive theory (Bandura, 2001), enables individuals to exercise work over their actions, with novelty amid uncertainty. The significance of self-leadership has gained renewed consideration in modern research, specifically in professional and educational frameworks. For instance, latest studies highlight its role in defending negative effects, by satisfying psychological needs for sovereignty, capability, and relatedness (Linnenborn & Borchert, 2025). Similarly, in academic areas, self-leadership significantly

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influences research productivity of university faculty (Doiron, 2023).

In spite of these advancements, gaps prevail in understanding self-leadership's application through varied cultural and sectoral contexts, especially in developing economies where organizational inertia and external pressures may weaken its effects.

2.3 Employee Performance

Employee performance, a keystone for organizational success, which means that to what extent individuals attain their job-related goals (Ren, Deng, Men, & Boudouaia, 2025). In SOEs perspective, particularly within Pakistan employee performance plays a key role in driving public sector effectively amid challenges like bureaucratic inertia and economic instability (Sayed et al., 2025). Modern studies highlight its role in raising organizational flexibility, specifically in developing economies where SOEs face exclusive structural and cultural constraints (Teofilus, Ardyan, Sutrisno, Sabar, & Sutanto, 2022).

The importance of employee performance extends afar individual output, influencing organizational effectiveness in sectors critical for national development (Ibrahim et al., 2024). Such as in SOEs of Pakistan where inadequacies mostly curtail from organizational inertia, even high-performing employees can drop operational outcomes (Asim et al., 2025). Modern research highlights the relationship between employee performance and stiff bureaucratic settings, which can erode trust and engagement (Sayed et al., 2025). However, in current digital transformation era where lot of uncertainties prevailing there is a great need for adaptive performance strategies to support growing industry demands (Yu, Hao, & Wang, 2020). This study examines the influence of organizational inertia on employee performance, with self-leadership as a moderating variable, directing to deliver actionable insights for SOEs in Pakistan.

2.4 Organizational inertia and Employee Performance

Organizational inertia, described as organization's confrontation towards change due to rigid routines, inflexible structures, and traditional norms has been documented as a significant impact to performance in growing business landscapes (Kavindi & Kularathne, 2024). Modern studies have progressively motivated to examine the direct and indirect effects of inertia on employee performance, like productivity and job efficacy. In unstable settings, inertia aggravates the negative effects of performance by decreasing adaptive behaviors (Kuzmanov, 2025). Some others suggest that inertia collectively, such as individual, team and organizational level erodes innovative performance (L. Liu & Wang, 2025). Recent empirical surveys constantly explore a negative correlation between organizational inertia and employee performance, a study on Egyptian travel agencies and hotels establish that inertia directly weakens organizational performance by decreasing employee innovative behavior (Ibrahim et al., 2024). Encompassing to broader corporate settings, research showed inertia's injurious role in innovation process, leading to reduced employee performance (Tewolde, Tewolde, & Tewolde, 2024). On the basis of above literature, I hypothesize it as;

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H1: Organizational inertia has negative impacts on employee performance

2.5 Self-Leadership Moderating Organizational Inertia and Employee Performance

Self-leadership is an individual's ability to control their emotions and behaviors through vigilant strategies such as self-observation, goal-setting and productive thought patterns (Houghton, Dawley, & DiLiello, 2012). It is a process of self-regulation, which empowers employees to exert proactive behaviors to control their working environment in stimulating organizational perspectives (Linnenborn & Borchert, 2025). In the framework of organizational inertia, self-leadership has appeared as a critical moderator in mitigating inertia's negative effect on employee performance (Qalati et al., 2022). By empowering employees to navigate rigid organizational settings, self-leadership encourages adaptive behaviors, inherent motivation, and innovative offerings to enhancing performance instead of inertial constraints (J. Zhang, Zhang, Lu, & Zhang, 2022).

Recent empirical research provides robust evidence for self-leadership's moderating role across diverse organizational settings. For instance, a study demonstrated that self-leadership significantly moderates the relationship between inertial obstacles and performance (Lee, Choi, Jones-Jang, Kim, & Kenski, 2025). Studies also argued that self-leadership in public sector environments, moderates the impact of inertia on employee performance through normative commitment (Asim et al., 2025). Self-leadership in team settings, verdict that it significantly moderates the relationship between organizational inertia and work role performance (Jamaluddin et al., 2025). Instead of these developments substantial research gap is existing, especially in the perspective of State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) in developing countries such as Pakistan, where organizational inertia is prominent due to rigid hierarchies and resource constraints (Sayed et al., 2025). Therefore, I propose it as;

H2: Self-Leadership significantly moderate the relationship between Organizational inertia and employee performance

2.6 Self-Leadership and Employee Performance

The direct impact of self-leadership on employee performance is ideally rooted in Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 2001), which means that self-regulatory processes like goal-setting and self-efficacy enhanced employee performance outcomes. In manufacturing companies, the study examined that self-leadership enhance employee performance through self-direction and motivation (Goldsby, Neck, & Mathews, 2021). In some cases, self-leadership help out to increase the effectiveness of organization by focusing on goal oriented behaviors, that ultimately enhance employee productivity and performance (Arslan et al., 2023)

In the same way, study conceptualized it that self-leadership as a preemptive tool that can foster high performance work systems, through enhancing employee autonomy and effectiveness in vibrant work environments (Harari, Williams, Castro, & Brant, 2021). After post pandemic era when mostly works has been shifted at home, its highlight the role of self-leadership for effective role performance by

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shifting themselves towards motivational states (Qalati et al., 2022). Another extended this by presenting that self-leadership has a significant positive effect on employee performance specifically in service-oriented roles (Konradt, Brombacher, Garbers, & Otte, 2019). This review emphasizes the need for empirical developments to upgrade the application of self-leadership in globally digital based working platforms. Hence I propose it that;

H3: Self-Leadership positively influence employee performance.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Sampling Design and Data Collection

Employees working in different sectors of state owned enterprises, such as power and energy, transport, communication, and financial sector, were the target population for this study. Due to the distinctive role for the country's GDP growth and employment, these sectors were selected. Employees of SOEs were preferred here due to their traditional bureaucratic experience where inertia is fostering and negatively impacts performance outcomes (Zolak Poljašević et al., 2025). Their continuing privatization highlights the need to observe and report on the restructuring of state-owned enterprises (SOEs).

The target population consists upon full-time employees working at top ranked levels, having supervisory positions and whose experience must be more than one year (Reisinger & Mavondo, 2007). This wide-ranging and diverse population was selected to improve generalizability. Because of mixed population multistage sampling technique (stratified cluster random sampling) was used to collect data (Creswell et al., 2021). Firstly, I stratify the whole target population into four sectors, power and energy, transport, communication and finance sector due to their key importance for economic growth. Secondly, I select comparative allocation method, means that random selection of organizations from each strata. At the end clustering method was chosen due to the non-availability of complete list of employees, for fulfilling the criteria.

Questionnaire based survey was used to collect data from the respondents because information I needed was about behaviors and attitudes (Scandura & Williams, 2000). The study directed a sample size of 400, but to confirm precision, 650 questionnaires were dispersed through numerous digital platforms, like Facebook and WhatsApp, accompanied by personal visits. For data analysis Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique was used in this study. According to Kyriazos & Stalikas (2018) sample size must be larger than 200 replies to meet the minimum condition for SEM. However for multivariate studies it has been suggested that this proportion is 5 respondents against each element (Reisinger & Mavondo, 2007). According to Reisinger & Mavondo (2007) the study's sample will be based upon 300 to 400 respondents. As per research ethics. It was guaranteed that the confidentiality of the respondents must be maintain.

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3.2 Measures

In this study previously validated measurement scales were employed because of their proved validity and reliability. OI was measured by 13-item scale adopted from Allcorn & Godkin, (2008), and further it is used by Ibrahim et al., (2024) which shows its Cronbach alpha values $\alpha=0.747$, $\rho=0.853$, and $\alpha=0.879$. SL was calculated by using the scale established by Houghton et al., (2012) which is originally consist upon nine items but only six items were engaged for analysis because of their empirical acceptability. After that the scale is adopted by Konradt et al., (2019) which displays its alpha value 0.80. Similarly EP was evaluated through 13-item scale developed by Koopmans et al., (2016) and then it is used by Amah, (2022) represent the alpha value 0.76. Generally, all of the constructs that are used in this research were well recognized and ensuring robust content validity. The adoption of empirically maintained instruments increases the soundness of study's measurement model.

3.3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

4. RESULTS

4.1 Sample Profile

In this research demographically various categories used such as gender, age, education, organizational experience and the working sector of employees. Descriptive test was employed to evaluate the separate result of each category as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Demographics

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	309	77.2
	Female	91	22.8

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Age	20-30 Years	104	26
	31 to 40 Years	126	31.5
	41 to 50 Years	102	25.5
	51 to 60 Years	68	17
Education	Bachelors	123	30.8
	Masters	163	40.8
	Professional	107	26.7
	Any Other	7	1.7
Organization Experience	1 to 5 years	103	25.8
	6 to 10 Years	143	35.8
	11 to 15 Years	82	20.4
	More than 15 Years	72	18
Working Sector	Power and Energy	131	32.8
	Transport	65	16.3
	Communication	91	22.8
	Financial	113	28.2

4.2 Measurement Model Assessment

To evaluate the overall model assessment descriptive analysis shows that data is normally distributed as shown in Table 2 which represent values according to the threshold of 2.0 and 7.0 for skewness and kurtosis respectively. Data is normal if skewness is between -

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2 to +2 and kurtosis is between -7 to +7 Hair et al. (2017).

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Table 2: *Descriptive*

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Kurtosis	Skewness
CP	4.198	0.650	0.076	-0.435
TP	4.655	0.796	-0.056	-0.546
OI	3.230	0.679	0.874	0.557
SL	4.170	0.473	-0.678	-0.787

To evaluate the construct reliability and convergent validity this research applied two step indicator approach for measuring EP and one step for SL and OI. Table 3 shows that outer loading values of all elements were above 0.70, which displays strong item reliability (Hair et al., 2021). To confirm the internal reliability of the construct Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability test were performed, represent values above the recommended threshold of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2021). AVE values that are above the minimum standard of 0.50 validate the convergent validity of whole construct (Larckel, D.F dan Fornell, 2016). Generally, the reliability and validity of the first-order measurement model was accepted by the results.

Table 3: *Constructs Validity and Reliability*

	Outer loadings	Cronbach Alpha	Composite reliability	AVE
CP1 <- CP	0.856	0.953	0.959	0.747
CP2 <- CP	0.891			
CP3 <- CP	0.891			
CP4 <- CP	0.789			
CP5 <- CP	0.886			
CP6 <- CP	0.873			
CP7 <- CP	0.865			
CP8 <- CP	0.860			
SL1 <- SL	0.885	0.944	0.954	0.774
SL2 <- SL	0.895			
SL3 <-SL	0.852			
SL4 <- SL	0.871			

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SL5 <- SL	0.894			
SL6 <- SL	0.881			
OI1 <- OI	0.741	0.959	0.963	0.667
OI10 <- OI	0.806			
OI11 <- OI	0.764			
OI12 <- OI	0.796			
OI13 <- OI	0.800			
OI2 <- OI	0.852			
OI3 <- OI	0.868			
OI4 <- OI	0.880			
OI5 <- OI	0.863			
OI6 <- OI	0.780			
OI7 <- OI	0.903			
OI8 <- OI	0.763			
OI9 <- OI	0.782			
TP1 <- TP	0.883	0.942	0.956	0.813
TP2 <- TP	0.891			
TP3 <- TP	0.911			
TP4 <- TP	0.905			
TP5 <- TP	0.916			

Heterotrait–Monotrait (HTMT) and Fornell-Larcker’s methods were applied to ensure discriminant validity of whole construct. HTMT values were below the suggested threshold of 0.85 and Fornell–Larcker test endorse the discriminant validity of construct.

Table 4: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) - Matrix

	CP	OI	SL	TP
CP				
OI	0.163			
SL	0.156	0.399		

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TP	0.816	0.249	0.176	
Table 5: Fornell-Larker criterion				
	CP	OI	SL	TP
CP	0.864			
OI	-0.211	0.817		
SL	0.191	0.357	0.880	
TP	0.770	-0.255	0.187	0.902

In the second-order measurement model, TP and CP were used to measure EP. According to the recommended criteria for assessment the second-order measurement model was considered reliable (Sarstedt, Hair, Cheah, Becker, & Ringle, 2019). Table 6 confirms the internal consistency, reliability and convergent validity of second-order constructs.

Table 6: Measurement Model for 2nd Order Constructs

	Outer loadings	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
LV scores - CP <- EP	0.934	0.877	0.942	0.890
LV scores - TP <- EP	0.952			

Concludedlly, after establishing adequate reliability and validity for all constructs, we are prepared for the next stage of investigation, the assessment of the structural model to test the hypothesized relationships.

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4.3 Structural Model Assessment

Figure 1 Structural Model Assessment (Path Coefficient, T-values and p-value)

Table 7: Path coefficients

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	VIF
OI -> EP	-0.323	-0.322	0.056	5.736	0.000	1.864
SL -> EP	0.158	0.164	0.033	4.801	0.000	2.674
SLX OI -> EP	0.390	0.390	0.040	9.667	0.000	2.469

PLS technique was used to test all research hypothesis and to attain accurate results extensive bootstrapping method was applied. The results of PLS-SEM provides solid empirical support about the hypothesized relationships. VIF threshold values showing that there is no any multicollinearity concerns (Hair et al., 2021). The structural model depicts that OI has a significant negative influence on EP ($\beta=-0.323$, $t=5.736$, $p<0.001$) and SL has a significant and positive impact on EP ($\beta=0.473$, $t=5.234$, $p<0.001$). in contrast, there is highly significant

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indirect effect of SL between OI and EP ($\beta = 0.390$, $t=9.667$, $p<0.000$), demonstrating that SL effectively moderate the OI and EP relationship.

Table 8: R-Square

	R-square	Adjusted R-square
EP	0.223	0.217

The R-square indicates that OI, SL and their interaction collectively explain 22.3% variance in EP which suggest that model has a moderate explanatory power. It also suggests that there may be some other variables excluded from the study that meaningfully explain the variance of EP.

Table 9: f-Square

	EP
EP	
OI	0.201
SL	0.028
SL x OI	0.272

The findings of f-square also validate the R-square pattern, as OI displays a moderate effect on EP ($f^2 = 0.201$) while SL has a minor direct effect on EP ($f^2 = 0.028$), however there is a substantial combined effect of SL and OI on EP ($f^2 = 0.272$). Collectedly, the outcomes of f-square and R-square significantly supporting the suggested moderation model.

4.4 Moderation Analysis

Moderation analysis was applied to tests whether the power of relationship alters at different levels of SL. Moderation effect was employed by adopting the method of Baron & Kenny, (1986).

Table 10: Moderation Analysis

Relationship	β	STDEV	t- Values	p-values	BI (2.5%;97.5%)	Decision
SL x OI -> EP	0.400	0.041	9.775	0.000	0.319;0.480	Accepted

The results depicted that SL positively and significantly moderates the relationship between OI and EP, ($\beta = 0.400$, $t=9.775$ and $p<0.001$). Therefore, it is established that the moderator SL has a significant positive effect on the relationship between OI and EP, which is also verified by the simple slope analysis as shown in Figure 2.

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Figure 2 Interaction Effect of SL on OI and EP

5. DISCUSSION

The findings of the current research strongly accepted the proposed hypothesized model with significant and realistic validation that organizational inertia established by rigid routines and inelastic structure inserts a robust negative impact on employee performance within SOEs of Pakistan (Moradi et al., 2021). This negative affect is mostly due to the traditional and legacy based operational system that disowned environmental changes and avoid modern operational technique specifically based upon AI which systematically erode employee motivation, job satisfaction and performance outcomes (Perera, 2025).

Recent observed studies specifically industries having vibrant environment where rigidity towards change stifles adaptability widely supporting H1 that organizational inertia has adverse impacts on employee performance. For instance, a study supports it as that inertia has negatively affect digital transformation, subsequently decline the efficiency of employees (Ghonim, Goda, Khashaba, Elstouhy, & Khashan, 2025). The study's findings are supported by the earlier outcomes which acknowledged that organizational inertia

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negatively affect adaptability and employee performance outcomes specifically in developing economies. Accompanying this, the study reveals that inertia creates uncertainty in today's vibrant business environment reducing overall performance of employees (Ibrahim et al., 2024). Innovation and creativity of employees also suffer in inertia based culture where novel ideas are suppressing because of change resistance (Knotts et al., 2022). However, these opposing studies do not reverse predominant impacts in literature.

Accompanying with main relationship and to avoid its negative outcomes, self-leadership emerges as a crucial moderator which significantly mitigate the damaging effects of inertia on employee performance outcomes by positive mind set and intrinsic goal setting among employees (Ghonim et al., 2025). So, H2 is accepted here because various studies provide robust support to this hypothesis that self-leadership moderates the relationship between the main intensive relationship of organizational inertia and employee performance and erode the effects of inertia. Such as a study demonstrated that strict policies and practices may decline the performance of employees but employees who have self-managed and goal oriented can mitigate the negative effects of inertia (Ryhänen, 2020). Similarly, another examined that in inertial settings where employee's performance is consistently effected entrance of self-leadership as a strategic technique plays an important role (Jamaluddin et al., 2025). Another reading accepted that self-leadership as a moderator significantly erode the stress from inertial culture and empower individuals with growth opportunities (Ruch, 2023). On opposing side some studies hypothesized that in predictable environment where economic and political situation is stable, high level of self-leadership may worsen the overall performance of the organization because of over reliance of individuals on personal efforts and misaligned from organizational goals (Ryhänen, 2020). Generally, the accepted studies are dominated here with quantification that moderation create variance and erode the harmful effects of inertia.

H3 is also accepted and have a strong support from the various empirical researches especially in energetic working environment that self-leadership directly influences employee performance. Such as, studies found that self-determination is a key indicator to enhance performance especially in remote work settings (Gagné et al., 2022). Employees who have high level of self-leadership establish greater self-governing capacity and displays high performance even in bureaucratic environments (Martela, 2019), an outcome of the study which provide great support to this research applicable into the unique organizational context. Another study also aligns with the findings that self-leadership plays important role to build resilience among employees and enhance creativity and performance among employees (Khahan, Vrabcová, Prompong, & Nattapong, 2024). In rigid bureaucratic structures self-leadership plays a distinguished role to mitigate the effects of inertia on employee performance (Ugoani, 2021). Likewise, another study also demonstrated that self-leadership boost intrinsic motivation of employees and build positive behaviors (Su & Hahn, 2025).

Evidences against the study are very rare but existing, such as a study inspected that excessively structured and high pressure

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environments where employees use excessive self-punishment approach for internal motivation sometimes decrease the performance of employees (de Vel-Palumbo, Woodyatt, & Wenzel, 2018). This evidence which negate hypothesis acceptance is interesting but requires replication. Overall with the help of supporting studies hypothesis is strongly accepted. The current study provides a clear platform to better explain the theoretical advancements and reforms for the SOEs of Pakistan. These improvements may be the self-encouragement programs and other training workshops. By assimilating these dynamics through moderation analysis, the current research extends contemporary discourse on individual's performance effectiveness specifically in state owned organizations.

5.1 Theoretical Implications

The acceptance of proposed model in current study provide a substantial framework for the implication of organizational inertia, self-leadership and employee performance outcomes specifically in state owned enterprises in Pakistan. By authorizing a significant negative influence of organizational inertia on employee performance, the findings extend organizational inertia theory beyond its traditional focus on structural and strategic rigidity at the macro level to reveal its detrimental micro-level consequences on individual task execution, motivation, and overall productivity in highly bureaucratic public-sector contexts (Hannan & Freeman, 1984). Additionally, the substantial moderating effect of self-leadership presents a serious emergent mechanism that links organizational inertia and self-leadership theories in a unique way. The results also validate that employees who have high self-leadership level and positive thought patterns display durable ability and skill to tackle the harmful effects of inertia (Aslam et al., 2024).

Jointly, these insights extend a more participative theoretical framework through evaluating macro and micro level constraints about inertia, contributing to mitigate the employee performance outcomes in public sector economies (Ashok, Al Badi Al Dhaheri, Madan, & Dzandu, 2021). The study thus provides a basic background for future research with some other effective moderators for inertia driven performance simulations, which displays more understanding about the individual flexibility during change situations.

5.2 Practical Implications

The pragmatic authentication of our suggested model transmits thoughtful and practical suggestions and implications for HR managers, and policymakers regarding Pakistan's State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs), which consistently faces annual losses due to inefficiencies, governance inflexibility and avoid disrupt changes. As study highlighted the harmful effects of organizational inertia on employee performance, managers and leaders of SOEs must consider and prioritize creativities to reduce bureaucratic rigidities, like empowerment of employees and create novelty to enhance productivity.

Moreover, Self-leadership as a moderator suggest that targeted motivational training programs can empower employees to proactively route out the inertial barriers and its negative impacts on employee outcomes. Specifically, in the context of Pakistani SOEs where

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organizational inertia with its rigid practices is largely rooted HR developmental trainings and seminars about self-leadership and self-motivation can produce resilient employees who systematically tackle the damaging effects of inertia.

At the top management level such policies should be adopt that highlight the importance of self-leadership motivational workshops and discourage the resilience against environmental change, to better align organizational strategies with current market demand which eventually upgrade these entities and make them more competitive. These legal and lawful practices potentially not only enhance the employee performance but also increase the fiscal sustainability of Pakistani public sector organizations.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RECOMENDATIONS

The cross-sectional design focuses only causal relationship in this study but fails to detent temporal variations in inertia, self-leadership, and employee performance outcomes (Jamaluddin et al., 2025). Furthermore, self-reported data increases the risk of common method variance, which may inflate the observed relationships (Khan, Li, Chughtai, Mushtaq, & Zeng, 2023). Another is, current research limit its generalizability due to the only focused on public sector with a specific cultural context, as institutional environments may differ accordingly (Hussain & Mohtar, 2017). Added here, the single moderator is considered and ignore some other credible mediators and moderators such as autonomous leadership, power system and personal agency (Arslan et al., 2023).

In future the research should adopt longitudinal design and establish causality to examine how self-leadership effectively work during institutional reforms. The model can be extendable to other private sectors, such as telecommunication and banking sector with different cultural context to enhance the generalizability. Finally, the study can be done in future with comparative analysis of two different cultures, like Pakistan (Developing economy) vs China (Developed economy) (Arslan et al., 2023).

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